

Role of Women in Religion

Mrs.Sunitha Evelyn Christy

Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, The American College, Madurai

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Christy, Sunitha Evelyn, and A. Sebastianmahimairaj OCD. "Role of Women in Religion." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 40–43.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551332>

Rev.Dr.A.Sebastianmahimairaj OCD

*Research Supervisor, Assistant Professor of Rural Development Science
Arul Anandar College, Madurai*

Abstract

Women have played key roles in religions throughout the world, though they are frequently less visible on the institutional level. While women have been active within their religions for millennia, our understandings of women's contributions to their faith communities, as well as the ways in which religious worldviews have helped to shape cultural gender roles, have only fairly recently become the subject of research. This topic has central relevance for many of our key cultural debates. Women have always been interested in religion and been extremely active in religion; in fact they've been central to all the world's religions.

Keywords: women, religion, culture, gender roles, institutionalization of religion

Introduction

Women have played key roles in religions throughout the world, though they are frequently less visible on the institutional level. While women have been active within their religions for millennia, our understandings of women's contributions to their faith communities, as well as the ways in which religious worldviews have helped to shape cultural gender roles, have only fairly recently become the subject of research. This topic has central relevance for many of our key cultural debates. Women have always been interested in religion and been extremely active in religion; in fact they've been central to all the world's religions. Historically women have been able to play very significant roles in religion. Nuns, for example, in the Christian tradition had huge power at certain times in history, acting as very independent groups doing their own thing without a great deal of clerical control.

Hinduism and Women

As Dr.s. Radhakrishnan has put it, Hindustan is the way of life rather than an institutionalised religion. It is as old as human civilisation. itself as it embodies human beings, formulation regarding the creation of this universe and its creator. It is polytheistic in the sense that every object of this universe, both living and non living is considered sacred and worthy of worship. Hinduism can be studied at different levels through the abstract and mystical ideas present in the Vedas and Upanishads or through the symbolic representation of

these abstract ideas in the form of myths and legends, or through their interpretation's manifested in the form of social customs and traditional practices, rituals, rights etc. In Hindu scriptures which are many and mostly descriptive, the concept of God the Brahman is gender free – neither male nor female. But when one considers the Hindu myths, the legends, religious customs and practises one can come across many instances of gender discriminations.

Women in Vedic India

The Aryan invasion and the vedic inculcation are almost synonymous. The Aryan brought with them their patriarchal social structure. It is said that the status of Indian woman in the Vedic age was much higher than that of women in any other early society. There were two types of women Sadyodavhinis, those who get married and take care of homes and Brahmavadinis, those who pursued studies and remained unmarried. In the later Vedic period, very few women chose to be Brahmavadinis, they preferred marriages. The erosion thus started. The marriage and its accompanying rituals, and declaration Mahabhartha and the Ramayan sought to it that the women were well bound in golden shackles.

Manu and Women

Manu and his unquestionable Manu Smiriti (code of Manu) converted the golden fetters into an iron one. Manu's codified pronouncements on women might have been derived from the Mahabharatha, his Anushashan Pradecees that:

“There is nothing that is more simple than a women verily omen are the roots of all evil”

No one seemed to recall that once the women had been strong, capable of composing hymns, holding philosophic discussions, and fighting in the battle fields if need to be Manu reduced them to a cipher with a passage:

“By a girl by a young women, or even by an aged one, nothing must be done independently, even in their own house. In childhood she is subject to her father, in youth to her husband, when her lord is death to her sons; a women must never be independent”.

Marriage and Women

Marriage and its corollary rituals are probably the factors to keep a Hindu women subservient forever. Manu's customary laws were codified into the hindu law later by the British rulers. The srutis and smiritis gave a pseudo status to women that their presence and sanctions in a vedic ceremony were absolutely inevitable, this law consequently led to child marriages and polygamy. The non vedic rituals framed in the worship of god, infiltrated themselves in the cultural stream, the practise of which had been willingly adopted by women.

Asceticism and Women

The Bhagavadgita's message of detachment of women from materialism and an option of spiritual came to the synonymous with the resistance of sexual instinct and ascetic practises respectively. This was severe blow to honour of hindu women. Women were considered not only to be hurdles in the spiritual attainments but also to practise aesceticism. They can attain salvation only through the bhakti yoga. That is, they have to show the single minded devotion either to their husband or to a deity.

Women Mystics

We have a few women mystics like Karaikkal Ammaiyar, Andal, Meera Akkamma Devi and so on who have recorded their mystical experiences in their memorable poetry and they prove that women does not need a man intermediary between herself and god.

Christianity and Women

In the story of Creation, the man said “this is now bone of my bones, for she was taken out of man”, Genesis 2:23. When Eve was created the purpose of their companionship was to love and to cherish but when sin entered it became to desire and to dominate and woman began to be considered property to man in the patriarchal society of the Israelites. Yet many women did prove to be successful in different areas.

The following are some of the women of distinct qualities and achievement in the Old Testament.

- Two nurses who saved Moses had the ethical guts or courage to violate King Pharaoh’s law, Exo.1:16-9
- Pharaoh’s daughter brought up a Jewish child without her father’s knowledge (Exo. 2:6-10)
- Miriam led people in the desert. (Exo. 15:20-21)
- Reheb - hid the spies (Joshua 2:3-7)
- Daborah – served a judicial and a political leader (Judges 4:4-5)

Social Practises Related to Women

- Property rights for women: Number 27 and 36. Moses had to change the laws in order to share the property for women.
- Widow’s marriage was in vogue – Roth 4:5
- Women slaves: It was said clearly that the women slaves must not be misused or forced to prostitution. (Exo 20 and 23)
- Purification ceremony if a woman delivered a boy baby she is unclean for 40 days but for a female child 80 days. Again female child cannot be sacrificed.

New Testament

The Sadducees and Pharisees tried to interpret Mosaic laws for their convenience in order to make the position of women complicated. Then the birth of Jesus through Virgin Mary in order to make the position of women complicated. Then the birth of Jesus through Virgin Mary brought radical change. Jesus talked to marginalized women eg Samaritan woman, John 4:14 – 42.

- He had friendship with Martha & Mary (Luke 10:38-42)
- His attitude towards a prostitute
- He resurrected a widow’s son. Luke 7:11-15
- He allowed Magdeline to anoint his feet Luke 7:36-39

After his resurrection, He first appeared to women who in turn became the first evangelists.

Muslim Women

The status of Muslim women has been misunderstood because of general of the true Islamic faith and due to the distortion of the media.

In the Medieval India with Muslim invasion of the country Purdah for women came as a social practice. Purdah is veiling their faces by women in the presence of outsiders or elderly men. Though the Quran authorizes women to come out of purdha when needed during war and epidemics, the religious leader totally disapprove of the appearance of women in public without burqa.

According to Islam a woman may not be married without being consulted and she could also obtain divorce if desired but in actual practise social stigma is attached to it and divorce is looked by down by others. Islamic law also lays down that if the husband divorce his wife he must pay her the “mehr” and give her a proper maintenance allowance as long as she remains unmarried or finds an alternative support. Shah Banocase, 1985 whether divorces or widowed/ sent she is at liberty to marry again.

Muslim personal law is based on the Shariat. The word Shariat literally means the roads to the watering place or the path to be followed; The Holy Quran, Sunna (the prophet's saying and practice) which is same – Divine in nature, Qiyas (analogy) and Ijma (consensus which are human in character form the Shariat. Hence the present position of Islamic women is not just determined by the Holy Quran but by other text too.

Conclusion

Women around the world have always been central in all religions. That's partly because women have always had a huge stake in developing their relationship with the divine, in getting closer to God, to what they see as the most true, the most beautiful, the most powerful; but also because women deal with the real everyday important issues of life and survival -with birth, with life, with marriage, with issues around illness and well being and of course death.

References

- Ahuja. ML. "Women in Indian Mythology", *Rupa Publications*, India. 2011.
Karen. L., & Garst. "Women vs Religion: The Case Against Faith and for Freedom", *Pitchstone Publishing House*, USA. 2018.
Shankar Rao. CN, "Sociology of Indian Society", *S.Chand Publishing House*. India. 2004.